

0. Design the process

- Have we invited diverse stakeholders to co-design the assessment? (e.g., ECRs, senior researchers, librarians, data stewards, bibliometricians, management)
- Are we using an established framework to structure discussions? (e.g., SCOPE, HumetricsHSS)
- Is there institutional mandate or long-term commitment for this reform? (e.g., CoARA Action Plan)

1. Start with what you value

- Have we agreed on core super-values guiding the assessment (e.g., openness, diversity, quality, excellence, collegiality)?
- Is there a value statement that considers SSH specificities (e.g., multilingualism, and diverse outputs, careers, methodologies)?
- Have we translated the value statement into operational sub-values that guide the assessment practice (e.g. recognising the individual's role in collaborative processes)?

2. Context considerations

- Are the criteria balanced (quantitative/qualitative) considering the level of assessment (e.g., individual, departmental, institutional, national, international)?
- Have we considered SSH-specific context factors? (e.g., multilingualism, citation behaviour, local focus of research)
- Have we defined 'Open Science' in a way that respects the SSH context? (e.g., defining open data considering ethical constraints)

3. Options for evaluating

- Have we considered diverse roles (e.g. CRediT roles) in the evaluation?
- Have we used a Narrative CV format for the evaluation?
- Have we used services from open infrastructures (e.g. OPERAS Metrics, GoTriple, PRISM, OpenAIRE Monitor, BIP! Scholar) rather than commercial databases?

- Have we considered alternatives to h-index, Journal Impact Factor, and citation counts?
- Are diverse outputs (e.g. exhibitions, software, artwork) recognised in the assessment?
- Are activities also valued (e.g. peer review, mentoring, teaching, societal engagement)?

4. Probe deeply

- Have we avoided the "Streetlight effect"? (i.e. measuring what is easy to monitor)?
- Could the indicators lead to gaming (outputs-for-numbers, predatory journals)?
- Have we identified risks with popularity metrics (e.g., views and downloads as vague proxies, outputs without DOIs being excluded)?
- Have we avoided superficial compliance (e.g., DMPs as checkboxes)?
- Have we guarded against structural biases (e.g., hierarchies, career stage)?
- Have we established mitigation strategies? (e.g. expert panels, guidelines for evaluators, recognition and criteria adjustments)

5. Evaluate your evaluation

- Was the process transparent and clearly communicated to all stakeholders?
- Does the evaluation still align with the original values defined at the start of the process?
- Did the evaluation effectively integrate institutional context and SSH-specific dimensions?
- Is there a formal feedback loop in place to review and refine criteria periodically?
- Were any unintended consequences identified (e.g., exclusion or misrepresentation) that require mitigation?
- Based on a cost-benefit analysis, were the results proportionate to the effort and resources invested (e.g., time-intensive peer reviews, administrative burden, manual data collection, the resulting workload for the team)?